

The physicochemical properties of some of the raw materials used in the present study are provided below:

Table 1.

Physicochemical Properties of the Raw Materials

Physicochemical Properties of the Raw Materials	Petroleum acid	1,2 – dibromopropane	Catalyst Tetrabutylammonium Bromide (TBAB)
Density, at 20°C, g/cm ³	0.9544	1.98	1.039
Boiling point, °C	120 – 190/6.65 MPa	141	102
Melting point, °C	–	~ -70	102 – 106
Molecular weight, g/mol	206	201.98	322.37
Acid value	272.53	–	–
Refractive index, n_{20}^D	1.4592	1.527 – 1.530	1.422

The synthesis of complex esters of naphthenic acids was carried out in the laboratory in two main stages. In the first stage, naphthenic acid reacted with sodium hydroxide to form the corresponding sodium salt. In the second stage, the obtained sodium naphthenate reacted with dibromopropane, resulting in the synthesis of the ester compound.

Initially, 50 mL of distilled water was added to a 100 mL three-necked flask. Then, 1.7 g of naphthenic acid was added, and under stirring, a 0.4 g solution of sodium hydroxide was gradually added dropwise. The mixture was stirred until completely dissolved and allowed to react for 10–15 minutes to ensure completion of the reaction. The progress of the reaction was monitored by pH measurements and adjusted until a neutral pH was achieved. The resulting sodium naphthenate was then separated from the aqueous phase and dried.

In the next stage, 2.81 g of sodium naphthenate was added to a 100 mL three-necked flask. Then, 2.02 g of dibromopropane and 0.16 g of the phase-transfer catalyst, tetrabutylammonium bromide (TBAB), were added. The reaction mixture was then supplemented with 30 mL of diethyl ether or 0.05 g of toluene as a solvent and stirred at 70–80°C for 4–6 hours.

After the reaction was complete, the mixture was cooled and separated into aqueous and organic phases using a separatory funnel. The organic phase was dried

with Na₂SO₄ and filtered. The solvent was then removed using a rotary evaporator, and the resulting product was analyzed. The purity and structure of the product were confirmed using FT-IR spectroscopy and nuclear magnetic resonance (¹H and ¹³C NMR) methods.

The obtained results showed that the synthesized product was a high-purity naphthenic ester, and the reaction yield ranged from 70–85%. The infrared (IR) and nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy results of the complex esters obtained in the process are as follows:

IR:1750 cm⁻¹ – C=O (carbonyl)1150 cm⁻¹ – C-O-C (ether)540 cm⁻¹ – C-Br**NMR:**¹H-NMR (δ, ppm)4.1–4.3 – Ether CH₂0.9 – CH₃

11.5 – Carboxyl proton (residual)

¹³C-NMR (δ, ppm)

173 – Carbonyl C

64–66 – OCH₂

This method is highly efficient and optimal for the synthesis of complex esters. After the completion of the process, the yield of the complex ester was 87%.

Table 2.

Physicochemical Properties of the Obtained Complex Ester

Sample	Density (g/cm ³)	T _{qay.} , °C	T _{freez...} , °C	T _{flash.} , °C	Mr
RCOOCH ₂ CHBrCH ₃	0.960	185 – 195/ 0.4 – 0.5 kPa	-23	250	458

TBAB is an appropriate catalyst for increasing interphase contact. It accelerates the reaction rate by 2–3 times and ensures a high yield under milder conditions.

The surface-active properties of the obtained ester were investigated, and it was found that it significantly

reduces the surface tension. Specifically, at a concentration of 1.0% by mass in water, the surface tension decreases from 72.2 to 29.5 dyn/cm.

The surface tension values of the obtained ester at the air-water interface are presented in the following table.

Surface-active Properties of the Obtained Ester at the Water-Air Interface, at 20°C

Ester concentration in water, mass %	Surface tension value, dyn/cm
0.1	56.3
0.25	46.7
0.5	38.5
1.0	29.5

Conclusion

An effective method has been developed for the synthesis of halogen atom-containing saturated esters of naphthenic acids derived from petroleum. This method is based on the interaction of sodium salts of the aforementioned naphthenic acids with halogen-containing saturated and unsaturated C₃ hydrocarbons in the presence of a phase-transfer catalyst, tetrabutylammonium bromide.

Optimal conditions for the synthesis of mono-esters with high yields through the interaction of sodium naphthenate with 1,2-dibromopropane in two-phase systems have been determined. The obtained mono-ester has been proposed as a surfactant.

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